

Network Infrastructure Design for Mabalacat City Police Station in Mabiga

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ABSTRACT

Reliable network infrastructure is essential for government institutions that depend on continuous communication, secure information exchange, and efficient operational coordination. This study proposed a network infrastructure design for the Mabalacat City Police Station to address existing limitations in connectivity, coverage, security, and scalability. The current network setup consists of a single wireless router serving approximately 10 to 30 users across multiple offices and operational rooms, resulting in weak signal coverage, intermittent connectivity, and limited network management capabilities. A descriptive-developmental research design was employed using Cisco's Prepare, Plan, Design, Implement, Operate, and Optimize (PPDIOO) framework. Data were gathered through site observation, informal interviews, and assessment of the existing network environment. The proposed design integrates a hybrid Local Area Network (LAN) and Wireless Local Area Network (WLAN), structured cabling, strategic wireless access point placement, Virtual Local Area Network (VLAN) segmentation, Access Control Lists (ACLs), Dynamic Host Configuration Protocol (DHCP), Network Address Translation (NAT), and inter-VLAN routing. The design follows a star topology to ensure centralized management, improved reliability, and future scalability. The proposed infrastructure is expected to enhance network coverage, strengthen security, improve communication efficiency, and support future expansion within the police station. The study provides a practical and scalable network solution that aligns with the operational requirements of law enforcement agencies and contributes to improved public service delivery.

Keywords: VLAN Segmentation, Hybrid LAN/WLAN, Network Security, Structured Cabling, Access Control Lists, Network Scalability

INTRODUCTION

Modern organizations increasingly rely on information and communication technologies to support daily operations, facilitate information sharing, and improve service delivery. In government institutions such as police stations, network infrastructure plays a critical role in ensuring effective communication, secure data management, and timely coordination among personnel. A reliable network system enables law enforcement agencies to process

reports, access databases, communicate internally and externally, and respond efficiently to public safety concerns (Rouil, 2021).

The Mabalacat City Police Station currently operates using a basic wireless network infrastructure composed of a single Wi-Fi router that provides internet connectivity to approximately 10 to 30 users. Although this setup supports basic communication and internet access, it presents several operational challenges. Weak wireless coverage, unstable connectivity, absence of structured cabling, lack of network segmentation, and limited security controls reduce the efficiency and reliability of network services across the station. These limitations affect communication, information sharing, and access to online resources necessary for law enforcement operations (Collier et al., 2021).

Government institutions increasingly require reliable and secure network infrastructures to support digital transformation initiatives, communication systems, and operational efficiency. The Department of Information and Communications Technology (DICT) emphasized the importance of secure network infrastructures in supporting government services and cybersecurity initiatives (DICT, 2024). Likewise, the Philippine National Police continues to strengthen its digital transformation programs to improve information management and communication systems across police units (PNP, 2023).

Previous studies have emphasized the importance of structured network design, wireless coverage optimization, network segmentation, and security mechanisms in improving organizational communication systems. Research on enterprise and government network infrastructures has demonstrated that properly designed networks enhance reliability, scalability, operational efficiency, and information security (Alharbi et al., 2022; Chen & Sun, 2024). Furthermore, studies involving Virtual Local Area Networks (VLANs) have shown that logical network segmentation improves traffic management, reduces congestion, and strengthens access control among departments (Djeddar et al., 2025; Liliana et al., 2023).

This study is based on the Input Process Output (IPO) conceptual framework. The Input component includes the existing network infrastructure, building layout, user population, device requirements, security requirements, and connectivity issues. The Process component consists of site observation, network assessment, requirements analysis, topology design, VLAN segmentation, IP addressing, security planning, simulation, and

validation through Cisco Packet Tracer using the PPDIIO framework (Hadi et al., 2025). The Output component is the proposed network infrastructure plan that includes a hybrid LAN/WLAN architecture, logical and physical topology, VLAN implementation, IP addressing scheme, security controls, and scalability recommendations.

Figure 1
Conceptual Framework

METHODS

This study employed a descriptive-developmental research design in developing a proposed network infrastructure for the Mabalacat City Police Station. The study focused on assessing the existing network environment, identifying connectivity and security issues, and developing a structured network infrastructure plan to address the identified limitations.

The study was conducted at the Mabalacat City Police Station located in Mabiga, Mabalacat City, Pampanga. The facility consists of eight functional offices and operational rooms, namely the Chief of Police Office, Police Clearance Office, Finance Office, Administrative Office, Investigation Office, Women and Children Protection Desk (WCPD) Room, Radio Room, and Conference Room. The station serves approximately 10 to 30 personnel who rely on network connectivity for communication, documentation, and information processing.

The development of the proposed network infrastructure followed Cisco's Prepare, Plan, Design, Implement, Operate, and Optimize (PPDIIO) framework (Hadi et al., 2025). During the Prepare phase, existing network problems and operational requirements were identified. During the Plan phase, building layout, user population, and connectivity requirements were assessed. During the Design phase, the proposed network topology, VLAN structure, IP addressing scheme, access point placement, and security configurations were developed. The Implement phase involved simulation and validation of the proposed design using Cisco Packet Tracer. The Operate and Optimize phases focused on

recommendations for future monitoring, maintenance, and expansion of the network infrastructure.

Data gathering was conducted through site observation, assessment of the existing network setup, documentation of room locations, identification of device placement requirements, and evaluation of connectivity issues. Information obtained during the assessment served as the basis for network planning and design.

The proposed network topology was a hybrid LAN and WLAN topology with the star topology. The design included the use of a centrally managed switch and wireless access points throughout the Chief of Police Office, Police Clearance Office, Finance Office, Administrative Office, Investigation Office, WCPD Room, Radio Room, Conference Room and Lobby Area. Access points were dedicated to office computers, smartphones, laptops and IP webcams to provide wireless connectivity. A secure remote connectivity and future extension capability of the network was also simulated with a GRE (Generic Routing Encapsulation) tunnel that was connected to an ISP router. VLAN segmentation, DHCP, NAT, inter-VLAN routing, and Access Control Lists (ACLs) were incorporated into the design. Cisco Packet Tracer was used to simulate and validate the proposed network configuration. The proposed design was evaluated through expert assessment using a structured evaluation questionnaire focusing on network architecture, security, scalability, reliability, and implementation feasibility. Responses were analyzed using weighted mean to determine the overall acceptability of the proposed network infrastructure design.

Table 1
Verbal Interpretation Scale Guide

Scale Range	Verbal Interpretation
3.26 – 4.00	Excellent
2.51 – 3.25	Good
1.76 – 2.50	Fair
1.00 – 1.75	Poor

The gathered data from the evaluation of the proposed network infrastructure plan will be analyzed using descriptive statistical methods, particularly the weighted mean, to determine the level of acceptability of the proposed design based on expert assessment. The responses collected from the evaluation questionnaire will be tabulated, summarized, and interpreted according to the identified criteria.

Notation 1
The formula for weighted mean

$$WM = \sum fx / N$$

The weighted mean will be used to measure the overall evaluation of the proposed network infrastructure plan in terms of network design, security, scalability, functionality, reliability, and implementation feasibility.

WM = Weighted Mean

$$\Sigma fx = \text{Sum of the weighted responses}$$

$$N = \text{Total number of responses}$$

RESULTS

The assessment of the existing network infrastructure at the Mabalacat City Police Station revealed several limitations affecting communication and operational efficiency. The current network relies on a single wireless router that provides connectivity to approximately 10–30 users distributed across multiple offices and operational rooms. As a result, weak wireless coverage, intermittent connectivity, and network congestion were observed, particularly in areas located farther from the router.

The assessment also identified the absence of structured cabling, dedicated wireless access points, managed switches, network segmentation, and advanced security mechanisms. These limitations increase the risk of unauthorized access, reduce network performance, and restrict the network's ability to accommodate future expansion.

To address these issues, a proposed network infrastructure was developed using a hybrid Local Area Network (LAN) and Wireless Local Area Network (WLAN) architecture. The proposed logical topology utilizes a star topology with a managed switch serving as the central distribution point for all network communications. The design incorporates Virtual Local Area Networks (VLANs), Dynamic Host Configuration Protocol (DHCP), Network Address Translation (NAT), inter-VLAN routing, Access Control Lists (ACLs), and a Generic Routing Encapsulation (GRE) simulation to support secure remote connectivity and future network expansion.

Figure 2

Logical Topology of Mabalacat City Police Station in Mabiga Network Design

The proposed physical topology was designed to provide organized device placement, structured cabling, and complete wireless coverage throughout the facility. Strategic placement of wireless access points enables connectivity across all offices and operational rooms, while Cat6 cabling supports reliable wired communication for critical network devices.

Figure 3

Proposed Physical Topology / Floor-Based Layout of Mabalacat City Police Station

Nine VLANs were established to logically separate departments and operational areas, improving network organization, security, and traffic management. Each VLAN was assigned a dedicated subnet to facilitate controlled communication between authorized users and departments.

The proposed infrastructure requires networking devices and materials that support secure, scalable, and reliable communication. These include a managed switch, ISP router, wireless access points, structured cabling components, and backup power systems.

Table 2

Verbal Interpretation Scale

Evaluation	Mean	Interpretation
Network Design and Architecture	3.26	Excellent
Security Architecture & Controls	3.19	Good
Compliance & Standards Alignment	2.96	Good
Risk Management	2.81	Good
Implementation Feasibility	3.37	Excellent
Resource & Cost Planning	2.81	Good
Technology & Compatibility	3.22	Good
Operational Planning	2.85	Good
Performance & Capacity Planning	2.89	Good
Documentation Quality & Completeness	3.70	Excellent
Governance & Review Readiness	2.81	Good
Validation & Expert Review	3.18	Good
Criteria		
Overall Mean	3.09	Good

The proposed Network Infrastructure Plan for the Mabalacat City Police Station was evaluated by three IT experts and achieved an overall mean rating of 3.09 (Good). The highest-rated criterion was Documentation Quality and Completeness (3.70, Excellent), indicating that the proposal was comprehensive, well-organized, and supported by sufficient technical information. Implementation

Feasibility (3.37, Excellent) and Network Design and Architecture (3.26, Excellent) also received high ratings, demonstrating confidence in the practicality and effectiveness of the proposed design. The lowest-rated areas were Risk Management, Resource and Cost Planning, and Governance and Review Readiness (all 2.81, Good), suggesting the need for more detailed planning in these aspects. Furthermore, Cisco Packet Tracer simulation results confirmed stable connectivity, successful GRE tunnel implementation, VLAN communication, and reliable wireless connectivity. Overall, the findings indicate that the proposed network infrastructure is suitable for deployment and capable of supporting the operational needs of the police station.

DISCUSSION

The findings of the study indicate that the existing network infrastructure of the Mabalacat City Police Station is insufficient to support the communication and operational requirements of a modern law enforcement institution. The reliance on a single wireless router has resulted in inadequate coverage, unstable connectivity, and limited security, which negatively affect communication efficiency and information accessibility.

The proposed network infrastructure addresses these issues through the integration of wired and wireless connectivity, structured cabling, VLAN segmentation, and enhanced security mechanisms. The use of a hybrid LAN and WLAN architecture provides both reliability and flexibility, enabling personnel to access network resources efficiently while maintaining stable communication channels.

The implementation of VLAN segmentation supports findings from previous studies that highlighted the benefits of logical network separation in reducing unnecessary traffic, improving performance, and strengthening security. By assigning dedicated VLANs to different offices and operational units, the proposed design minimizes broadcast traffic and limits unauthorized access between departments.

Strategic placement of wireless access points is consistent with the recommendations of El-Gendy et al. (2022), who emphasized the importance of proper access point placement in minimizing wireless interference and improving indoor wireless coverage. Likewise, the use of structured cabling aligns with the findings of Damir Blažević et al. (2024), who reported that organized cabling systems improve network reliability, scalability, and maintenance efficiency.

The implementation of ACLs enhances data protection by restricting communication between specific network segments and isolating public users from sensitive operational resources. Such security measures are critical in law enforcement environments where confidential information must be protected from unauthorized access (Rajabli, 2024).

The proposed infrastructure demonstrates how modern networking practices can improve communication efficiency, security, scalability, and operational effectiveness within government institutions. The design aligns with recommendations from previous literature regarding enterprise and government network environments (Alharbi et al., 2022; Chen & Sun, 2024).

CONCLUSIONS

The study successfully developed a proposed network infrastructure design for the Mabalacat City Police Station based on the identified operational and communication requirements of the institution. Assessment of the existing network environment revealed significant limitations in wireless coverage, network stability, scalability, and security.

To address these issues, a hybrid LAN and WLAN network architecture based on star topology, VLAN segmentation, structured cabling, wireless access point (AP), office computer integration into the wireless network, IP webcam integration, Dynamic Host Configuration Protocol (DHCP), Network Address Translation (NAT), inter-VLAN routing, and Access Control Lists (ACLs) was proposed, with the addition of a GRE simulation for a secure remote connection. The proposed design ensures better performance of the network, boosts security, manages traffic efficiently, enables wireless communication, and has the scope to be scalable to meet future organizational needs.

The proposed infrastructure is expected to improve communication reliability, data protection, network organization, and overall operational efficiency within the police station. The study demonstrates that a properly designed and scalable network infrastructure is essential in supporting the digital communication requirements of modern law enforcement agencies.

Future implementation of the proposed design is recommended to validate its effectiveness in a real-world environment and to identify additional improvements based on operational requirements and technological advancements.

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